

Antenna Array Optimization Strategies for Robust Direction Finding

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Abstract—This paper focuses on the optimization of uniform circular antenna array (UCA) structures equipped with analog combining networks for direction finding applications. For such type of arrays, the specific choice of the combining matrix has a crucial impact on the effective radiation pattern and the sensitivity of direction-of-arrival (DOA) estimation. A design framework for constructing the combining network is proposed that improves the DOA estimation performance of the array while limiting the probability of false detection of the DOA estimator to a desired value. In detail, we first derive an analytical expression for the false detection probability of the DOA estimator. This function together with the Cramér-Rao bound are then used to find the optimal combining matrix and array aperture size for a given number of sensor elements and combiner output (baseband) channels. We provide design examples to demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach.

Index Terms—uniform circular array, combining network, DOA estimation, optimization

I. INTRODUCTION

Direction finding using antenna arrays has been an active research field for many years [1]. When using arrays with large number of sensors and aperture size, the corresponding small beamwidth of the mainlobe may provide sufficient high resolution at a specific SNR threshold to separate the signal components impinging on the array with respect to their direction of arrivals (DOAs). However, enlarging the aperture size of conventional arrays by utilizing more sensors and active radio frequency (RF) channels may not always be feasible due to the high hardware costs and high power consumption of the array. Therefore, it has recently been proposed to apply the principle of compressed sensing (CS) [2], [3] to array processing. In particular, a CS array architecture was proposed in [5] that first linearly combines the M sensor signals in the analog domain by a passive combining network before passing them through a few number $V \leq M$ of RF channels for further processing. As only the signals of V RF channels need to be processed, the hardware and processing costs are reduced compared to the conventional array, while the aperture size remains identical. For this type of array, the design of the combining network has a significant influence on the achieved DOA estimation accuracy. It was shown in [4] that an improper design of the combining network may lead to effective arrays with high sidelobes. These high sidelobes

may lead to the detection of spurious peaks that cause false detections when using correlation-based DOA estimators. To alleviate the problem, a design that optimizes the effective beamformer spectrum with respect to a specific target sidelobe function was proposed in [4].

In this work, we present a design approach that optimizes both the aperture size and the combining network of uniform circular arrays (UCAs) with respect to specific performance requirements defined by the application. A typical requirement is that a desired false detection probability for DOA estimation is guaranteed at a specific minimum SNR of the signals impinging on the array. The proposed array design therefore aims to improve DOA estimation accuracy by minimizing the Cramér-Rao bound (CRB), while lowering the false detection probability of the DOA estimator to a desired threshold value.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the baseband system model for UCAs with analog combining networks. An approximation of the false detection probability of DOA estimation for single and two source scenarios is derived in Section III. In Section IV, we shortly review known results of the CRB. Section V addresses the constrained optimization of the combining network and array aperture size. In Section VI, exemplary results of the optimization for different array configurations are presented. Finally, Section VII concludes the paper.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

Consider an uniform circular array (UCA) having M equally spaced sensors receiving narrowband signals from D farfield transmitters. For simplicity, we assume that the antenna array and the transmitters are coplanar such that the DOAs of the source signals are located only in the azimuth plane. The $M \times 1$ complex baseband antenna array output vector $\mathbf{y}(k)$ then reads as

$$\mathbf{y}(k) = \sum_{d=0}^{D-1} \mathbf{a}(\varphi_d) s_d(k) + \mathbf{n}(k), k = 1, \dots, K, \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{a}(\varphi_d) \in \mathcal{C}^{M \times 1}$ is the array response for a source located at DOA φ_d , $s_d(k)$ is the complex baseband signal of the d -th source, and $\mathbf{n}(k)$ denotes the additive stationary,

white, zero-mean complex Gaussian noise which is independent of the source signals. The noise is assumed to be mainly caused by the LNAs and the sampling units. External noise sources such as sky noise are neglected. Therefore, we have $E\{\mathbf{n}(k)\mathbf{n}^H(k)\} = \sigma_0^2\mathbf{I}_M$ with σ_0^2 being the variance of $\mathbf{n}(k)$, and $E(\cdot)$ denotes the expectation operator, calculated by averaging over K snapshots. For a compact notation of (1), we define the array steering matrix $\mathbf{A} \equiv [\mathbf{a}(\varphi_0), \mathbf{a}(\varphi_1), \dots, \mathbf{a}(\varphi_{D-1})] \in \mathcal{C}^{M \times D}$ and the source vector $\mathbf{s}(k) = [s_0(k), s_1(k), \dots, s_{D-1}(k)]^T \in \mathcal{C}^{D \times 1}$ in a similar manner. The array output vector can then be expressed as

$$\mathbf{y}(k) = \mathbf{A}\mathbf{s}(k) + \mathbf{n}(k). \quad (2)$$

For an UCA with isotropic antenna elements, the array steering vectors $\mathbf{a}(\varphi_d)$ are given by

$$\mathbf{a}(\varphi_d) = [e^{j\zeta \cos(\varphi_d - \gamma_0)}, e^{j\zeta \cos(\varphi_d - \gamma_1)}, \dots, e^{j\zeta \cos(\varphi_d - \gamma_{M-1})}]^T, \quad (3)$$

where $\zeta = 2\pi r_0$ with r_0 being the normalized radius of the array over the wavelength, and $\gamma_m = 2\pi(m-1)/M$, ($m = 0, 1, \dots, M-1$) denotes the sensor location.

The system model in (2) allows for fully-digital array processing and presumes for each antenna element a dedicated radio frequency (RF) chain including a low-noise amplifier, filters, down-conversion, analog-to-digital conversion, and so on. For specific applications, however, such separate RF chains for each antenna element may come at a high cost and high power consumption of the array. In order to reduce the number of RF channels without loss in array aperture, the sub-arraying approach is applied, where the sensor outputs are first linearly combined in the analog domain and then passed through a number of RF chains to obtain the digital baseband signals. In this way, fewer RF chains than sensor elements are needed for signal processing in the digital domain. This approach has also been proposed in [5] as a compressive sensing receiver array architecture, see Fig. 1 for further illustration.

Let us denote by $\Phi \in \mathcal{C}^{V \times M}$ the complex-valued sensor array combining matrix. Assuming that the combining operation is implemented using analog phase shifters (with arbitrary phase angles), the entries of Φ are given by $[\Phi]_{i,j} = (1/\sqrt{V})e^{j\sqrt{-1}2\pi\phi_{i,j}}$, $\phi_{i,j} \in (0, 2\pi]$, where $[\Phi]_{i,j}$ denotes the (i, j) element of Φ . The complex baseband output vector of size $V \times 1$ with $V \leq M$ after the combining operation can be written as

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{y}}(k) &= \Phi \mathbf{A}\mathbf{s}(k) + \bar{\mathbf{n}}(k), \\ &= \sum_{d=0}^{D-1} \bar{\mathbf{a}}(\varphi_d) s_d(k) + \bar{\mathbf{n}}(k) \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where $\bar{\mathbf{n}}(k) \in \mathcal{N}_c(\mathbf{0}, \sigma_0^2 \mathbf{I}_V)$ denotes the $V \times 1$ complex Gaussian noise vector, and $\bar{\mathbf{a}}(\varphi_d) \equiv \Phi \mathbf{a}(\varphi_d)$. As observed in (4), the number of RF chains has been reduced from M to V . This reduction comes along with reduced hardware cost for the array as well as baseband processing effort. Moreover, based on (4), we define the SNR as $\rho = \sigma_s^2/\sigma_0^2$

Fig. 1. Compressive sensing array architecture.

with $\sigma_s^2 = E\{|s_d(k)|^2\}$ being the average signal power of the sources.

III. DERIVATION OF FALSE DETECTION PROBABILITY

In this section, an approximation of the false detection probability for a low-complexity correlation-based direction finder is derived. For the case of a single source as considered in the following, a correlation-based DOA estimator amounts to finding the DOA φ_0 corresponding to the global maximum in the beamformer spectrum $D(\varphi)$,

$$\varphi_0 = \arg \max D(\varphi) \equiv \bar{\mathbf{a}}^H(\varphi_0) \mathbf{R} \bar{\mathbf{a}}(\varphi_0), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{R} = E\{\bar{\mathbf{y}}^H(k)\bar{\mathbf{y}}(k)\}$ is the covariance matrix of the received signals. Note that for the case of a single source, the cost function in (5) is equivalent to the maximum likelihood (ML) cost function, and therefore, the correlation-based DOA estimator is equivalent to the ML estimator. A detector error is defined as the event where the global maximum in the beamformer spectrum $D(\varphi)$ is outside the mainlobe area (either 3-dB or null-to-null beamwidth). Thus, the error probability P_d is given by

$$P_d \equiv \text{Prob}(D(\varphi_0) < D(\varphi), \exists \varphi \in \mathcal{U}), \quad (6)$$

where $\varphi \in \mathcal{U}$ denotes the set of DOAs corresponding to the directions in the beamformer spectrum outside the mainlobe area, and

$$\begin{aligned} D(\varphi_0) &= |\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0^H \bar{\mathbf{y}}(k)|^2 = |\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0^H \bar{\mathbf{a}}_0 s(k) + \bar{\mathbf{a}}_0^H \bar{\mathbf{n}}(k)|^2, \\ D(\varphi) &= |\bar{\mathbf{a}}^H \bar{\mathbf{y}}(k)|^2 = |\bar{\mathbf{a}}^H \bar{\mathbf{a}}_0 s(k) + \bar{\mathbf{a}}^H \bar{\mathbf{n}}(k)|^2 \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

with $\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0 \equiv \bar{\mathbf{a}}(\varphi_0)$ and $\bar{\mathbf{a}} \equiv \bar{\mathbf{a}}(\varphi)$. A direct evaluation of (6) is analytically intractable. In order to proceed, we adopt the approach from [7], and approximate the continuous beampattern $b(\varphi, \varphi_0) = |\bar{\mathbf{a}}^H \bar{\mathbf{a}}_0| / (\|\bar{\mathbf{a}}\| \|\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0\|)$ of the antenna array by its discretized version

$$b^d(\varphi, \varphi_0) = \sum_{n=0}^N b(\varphi, \varphi_0) \delta(\varphi - \varphi_n), \quad (8)$$

where $\varphi_0 \notin \mathcal{U}$ and $\varphi_n \in \mathcal{U}$ for $n > 0$, are the directions corresponding to the mainlobe and the sidelobe peaks in the array beampattern, respectively, and N is the total number of the sidelobe peaks. Using (8), the false detection probability can now be approximated by

$$P_d \approx \text{Prob}\left(\bigcup_{n=1}^N \{D(\varphi_0) - D(\varphi_n) < 0\}\right). \quad (9)$$

Fig. 2. Analytical and numerical results of the false detection probability P_d for an 9-element UCA with different radii r_0 and no analog combining $\Phi = \mathbf{I}_9$, or randomly selected $\Phi \in \mathcal{C}^{5 \times 9}$ for a single random DOA.

In order to simplify the calculation, we apply the union bound [8] on (9), and obtain

$$P_d \leq \sum_{n=1}^N \text{Prob}(D(\varphi_0) - D(\varphi_n) < 0). \quad (10)$$

Now it remains to compute the individual probabilities $P_n \equiv \text{Prob}(D(\varphi_0) - D(\varphi_n) < 0)$, $\forall n$, where P_n denotes the probability that the n -th sidelobe peak is higher than the mainlobe peak. Here, the random variable $X_n(k) \equiv D(\varphi_0) - D(\varphi_n)$ is a linear transformation of the complex Gaussian random vector $\bar{\mathbf{y}}(k)$. Hence, $X_n(k)$ is also Gaussian distributed with mean

$$E\{X_n(k)\} = -|s(k)|^2 b_n + \sigma_0^2 g_n,$$

and variance

$$\text{VAR}\{X_n(k)\} = 2\sigma_0^2 |s(k)|^2 (|d_n|^2 (g_n - \|\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0\|^2) + (\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0^H \bar{\mathbf{a}}_0)^3),$$

where $\mathbf{c}_n \equiv \bar{\mathbf{a}}(\varphi_n)$, $n = 1, \dots, N$, $d_n \equiv \bar{\mathbf{a}}_0^H \mathbf{c}_n$, $b_n \equiv (\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0^H \bar{\mathbf{a}}_0)^2 - |d_n|^2$, and $g_n = \|\mathbf{c}_n\|^2 - \|\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0\|^2$. Therefore, P_n may be expressed as

$$P_n = Q \left[\frac{\sqrt{\rho} b_n - g_n / \sqrt{\rho}}{\sqrt{2|d_n|^2 (g_n - \|\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0\|^2) + 2(\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0^H \bar{\mathbf{a}}_0)^3}} \right], \quad (11)$$

where $Q(x) = 1/(2\pi) \int_x^\infty \exp(-u^2/2) du$.

A. Extension to Two-Source Scenario

The previous derivation of the false detection probability can be extended to the two source-scenario in a straightforward manner. Due to the lack of space, a detailed derivation is skipped and only the result is presented. We consider the detection of the strongest signal component and assume $\alpha = |s_2(k)/s_1(k)|^2 < 1$. The probability, P_n , that the n -th sidelobe peak is higher than the mainlobe peak can then be expressed

Fig. 3. False detection probability P_d for an $M = 9$ UCA with $r_0 = M/8$, $\Phi = \mathbf{I}_9$, or randomly selected $\Phi \in \mathcal{C}^{5 \times 9}$ for two sources with random DOAs and different power ratios α .

as

$$P_n = Q \left[\frac{\sqrt{\rho} (b_n - g_n / \rho - t_n - \alpha (|\bar{e}_n|^2 - |\bar{c}_0|^2))}{\sqrt{2(|d_n|^2 (g_n - \|\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0\|^2) + (\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0^H \bar{\mathbf{a}}_0)^3 + w_n + \alpha v_n)}} \right],$$

where $e_n \equiv \bar{\mathbf{a}}_1^H \mathbf{c}_n$, $c_0 \equiv \bar{\mathbf{a}}_1^H \bar{\mathbf{a}}_0$, $t_n \equiv 2\Re\{s_1 s_2^* (e_n d_n^* - c_0 \|\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0\|^2)\} / |s_1|^2$, $w_n \equiv 2\Re\{s_1 s_2^* (d_n e_n^* g_n + c_0^* b_n)\} / |s_1|^2$, and $v_n \equiv |e_n|^2 \|\mathbf{c}_n\|^2 + |c_0|^2 \|\bar{\mathbf{a}}_0\|^2 - 2\Re\{c_0 d_n e_n^*\}$.

B. Numerical Results

To assess the accuracy of the proposed error bound in (10), Monte Carlo simulations for 9-element UCAs with different array radii and different realizations of the combining matrix Φ were performed. The false detection probability P_d was computed by averaging over 10^5 random noise realizations. In the following we use the notation "(M, V) array" to refer to an M -element UCA with V baseband channels.

Fig. 2 shows the obtained numerical and analytical results using (10) for (9,9) arrays without analog combining of the received signals, i.e., $\Phi = \mathbf{I}_9$, and (9,5) arrays with analog combining where the phase values of $\Phi \in \mathcal{C}^{5 \times 9}$ are drawn from a uniform distribution. A single source located at a random DOA φ_0 and a single snapshot ($K = 1$) were assumed. It can be observed that a reasonable approximation of the false detection probability is obtained for high SNR values. Moreover, we see that the approximation gets closer to the numerical values when increasing the radius of the UCA and hence the number of sidelobe peaks in the array beampattern.

Fig. 3 shows the obtained results for a two source scenario with different random realizations of the two source locations. Two different power ratios α for the source signals were considered. The phase values of Φ were chosen randomly for the (9,5) array, whereas for the (9,9) array, $\Phi = \mathbf{I}_9$. As observed in this figure, the proposed approximation of the probability P_d gets tight at high SNR values for all array configurations. We also find that for specific realizations of

Φ , the probability remains high over the whole SNR range. This behavior is caused by very high sidelobe peaks in the array beampattern at angles differently to the DOAs of the two sources.

IV. CRAMÉR-RAO LOWER BOUND

In this section, we present results of the CRB derived in [6] for the signal model in (4). As the antenna array output vector is corrupted by white Gaussian noise, the associated CRB matrix is found to be

$$\text{CRB}(\Phi, r_0, \varphi_0, \dots, \varphi_{D-1}) = \frac{\sigma_0^2}{2K} \left(\Re\{\mathbf{Z} \odot \mathbf{R}_s^T\} \right)^{-1},$$

where $\mathbf{R}_s = \text{E}\{\mathbf{s}(k)\mathbf{s}^H(k)\}$ is the covariance matrix of the source signals, and \mathbf{Z} is a matrix that depends on the array beampattern and the combining matrix Φ ,

$$\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{D}^H \Phi^H \mathbf{B}^{-1} \Phi \mathbf{D}$$

with $\mathbf{B} = \mathbf{I} - \Phi \mathbf{A} (\mathbf{A}^H \Phi^H \Phi \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{A}^H \Phi^H$ and $\mathbf{D} = [\partial \mathbf{a}(\varphi_0)/\partial \varphi_0, \partial \mathbf{a}(\varphi_1)/\partial \varphi_1, \dots, \partial \mathbf{a}(\varphi_{D-1})/\partial \varphi_{D-1}]$. Note that for the single source case, \mathbf{Z} reduces to a scalar Z such that the CRB can be written as

$$\text{CRB}(\Phi, r_0, \varphi_0) = (2K\rho Z)^{-1}. \quad (12)$$

V. OPTIMIZATION OF COMBINING MATRIX AND APERTURE SIZE

The analytical expressions for the CRB and false detection probability presented in the previous section can now be used to optimize the combining matrix Φ and the sensor geometry with the objective to improve the DOA estimation accuracy of the array. In order to guarantee a desired value of P_d , the array beampattern must be designed such that the sidelobe peaks are limited to a given threshold value that depends on the minimum SNR ρ_{th} of the baseband signals. In addition, the range of directions from where the source signals are impinging on the array may influence the array optimization. As our focus is on design of UCAs, we do not restrict the DOA range of the impinging source signals. By this means, the array design can be formulated as a constrained optimization problem. Due to the space limitations, the optimization problem is only presented for the single source case,

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\varphi_0, \theta_{k,l}, r_0} \quad & \text{CRB}(\Phi, \varphi_0, r_0) \\ \text{subject to} \quad & P_d(\Phi, \varphi_0, r_0, \rho_{th}) < \epsilon_0, \\ & [\Phi]_{k,l} = \exp[\sqrt{-1}2\pi\theta_{k,l}], \text{ with } \theta_{k,l} \in (0, 2\pi], \forall k, l, \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $\text{CRB}(\Phi, \varphi_0, r_0)$ is given by the expression in (12). The optimization strategy in (13) aims to minimize the CRB and hence to improve the DOA estimation accuracy over the full angular range $(0, 2\pi]$, while lowering the false detection probability to a desired value ϵ_0 for a given SNR threshold point ρ_{th} . The VM entries of the combining matrix Φ are restricted to be complex values with unit amplitude. Together with the antenna array radius r_0 , thus, there are in total $VM+1$ free parameters in (13), which are optimized jointly.

Fig. 4. Comparison of normalized CRBs versus DOA for different UCA configurations.

Fig. 5. False detection probability P_d for 9-element UCAs with non-optimized $\Phi = \mathbf{I}_9$, optimized Φ , and random drawing phase values for Φ . $r_0 = 0.65$.

The first constraint and the objective in (13) are non-convex functions with respect to (Φ, φ_0, r_0) . The optimization problem is thereby a non-convex problem exhibiting a multi-modal cost function, where the optimal (global) solution can only be found by an exhaustive search strategy. Therefore, we apply a local minimizer to the above problem using an algorithm based on the interior-reflective Newton method [9], [10]. However, by using this algorithm the obtained solution strongly depends on the initialization of the parameters (Φ, φ_0, r_0) . Moreover, there is no guarantee that the global optimum is found. Therefore, the algorithm is applied several times where for each run the initialization of the parameters (Φ, φ_0, r_0) is different. By doing so, the obtained solution to (13) is likely to be sufficiently close to the optimal solution.

Fig. 6. False detection probability P_d for 9-element UCAs with non-optimized $\Phi = \mathbf{I}_9$, optimized Φ , and random drawing phase values of Φ . $r_0 = 0.9$.

VI. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, we present exemplary results of the array optimization to demonstrate the performance improvements achieved with our proposed design methodology. The optimization in (13) was performed for $M = 9$ element UCAs with analog combining of the sensor output signals via either an 5×9 or 7×9 matrix Φ . Thus, the optimized array provides either $V = 5$ or $V = 7$ active combiner output channels that can be used for DOA estimation. As a constraint, the threshold value ϵ_0 of the false detection probability P_d was set to 0.1 for both array configurations. The associated threshold SNR ρ_{th} was set to 9 dB. Similar to Section III-B, the notation “ (M, V) array” is used to refer to an M -element UCA with V baseband channels.

Fig. 4 shows the CRB of optimized (9, 7) and (9, 5) arrays for a single source. Here, the CRB is normalized such that it is independent of the SNR ρ and the number of snapshots K . The optimal normalized aperture radius was found to be $r_0 = 0.9$ and $r_0 = 0.65$ for these arrays, corresponding to a sensor element distance of $2r_0 \sin(\pi/M) \approx 0.62$ and $2r_0 \sin(\pi/M) \approx 0.45$ wavelengths, respectively. The figure also shows the CRBs of standard (9, 9), (7, 7) and (5, 5) arrays with no analog combining for identical normalized aperture radii. As expected, we observe that the standard (9, 9) array provides the lowest CRB compared to the two other array configurations. Moreover, we find that the CRB of the optimized (9, 5) array is lower than the CRB of the standard (5, 5) UCA. In Fig. 5, the associated false detection probabilities evaluated using the approximation in (10) for a single DOA in $\varphi_0 \in [-\pi, \pi]$ for different arrays with aperture radius $r_0 = 0.65$ are shown. As a further reference, the performance of an array with random realizations of the phase angles of Φ is depicted. It can be seen that the optimized array satisfies the false detection probability constraint such that $P_d \approx 0.1$ at an SNR of 9 dB. We also observe that the standard

(5, 5) array and the (9, 5) UCA with random combining perform significantly worse than the optimized array due to their higher sidelobes in the beamformer spectrum.

The false detection probabilities of the different array configurations with aperture radius $r_0 = 0.9$ are shown in Fig 6. In addition, the performance of an array with random phase angles for matrix Φ is shown as well. As observed, the optimized array performs significantly better than the standard (9, 9) UCA, and moreover it achieves the desired probability threshold $P_d \approx 0.1$ at an SNR of 9 dB. Once more, we find that the optimized design achieves a significantly lower false detection probability compared to an array design with randomly chosen angles for matrix Φ .

VII. CONCLUSION

We have proposed a novel design approach for improving the DOA estimation accuracy of uniform circular arrays equipped with analog combining networks. Based on an analytical expression of the false detection probability of the DOA estimator, it was shown that the antenna array design can be formulated as a constrained optimization problem. The combining network found as solution to this problem leads to arrays with optimum DOA estimation performance with respect to a desired probability of false detection of DOA estimation. Numerical result demonstrate the achieved performance improvements of the optimized arrays compared to standard arrays.

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